

ANALYSIS OF INFLATION FOR PROJECT EVALUATION

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Abstract. Risk prevention is an important strategy in any type of management. Including in the banking sector, sufficient plans and strategies are needed to assess monetary inflation. This article will tell you about them in detail.

Keywords: monetary policy, banking and finance, strategies, assessment and analysis process, etc.

Inflation processes are one of the most important and urgent issues of modern economy. Inflation directly affects the standard of living of citizens, economic growth and the development of the country as a whole. Therefore, economic and statistical analysis of inflation processes is necessary to understand and make effective decisions in this area. Inflation is an increase in the price level of goods and services throughout the economy. This can occur for various reasons, including increased demand, reduced supply of goods and services, increased production costs, etc. Inflation can manifest itself at different levels and take different forms, including hyperinflation, stagflation, deflation, and others. Economic and statistical analysis of inflation processes includes collection, analysis and interpretation of economic data related to inflation. To carry out such an analysis, it is necessary to have reliable and accurate data, including data on consumer prices, employment rates, GDP, money supply, inflation expectations, etc.

One of the main tools of economic and statistical analysis of inflation processes

is consumer price index (CPI). CPI reflects changes in the price level of consumer goods and services purchased by ordinary citizens. The CPI is usually calculated based on a weighted average of the prices of a certain set of goods and services that are most commonly purchased in a country. In general, the economic and statistical analysis of inflationary processes is the most important means of assessing the state of the country's economy, determining trends and features of inflationary processes, and determining measures to regulate them. The use of various models and methods allows for a comprehensive analysis of inflation and the development of effective measures for its management. Inflation usually occurs as a result of the demand for goods and services in the economy exceeding the supply of those goods and services. This leads to higher prices as businesses are able to charge more for their products due to higher demand. Alternatively, inflation can result from a reduction in the supply of goods and services, causing prices to rise as businesses compete for limited supply. Various statistical methods are used to analyze inflationary processes, including time series analysis, regression analysis, and forecasting. Time series analysis involves analyzing data over time to identify trends and patterns. Regression analysis is used to determine the relationship between various variables and inflation rates, while forecasting is used to predict future inflation rates based on past data.

Our international experience and statistical practice show that the most reliable, convenient and widespread method of measuring inflation is the index method. It includes the calculation of producer price indices using the chain method. Indices are calculated monthly and compared with the data of the previous month and the price level data of the same months of previous financial periods. They are determined by multiplying monthly indices over a long period of time. The applicable scale is the annual production value data used as the basis for calculations. The index method can be used to assess the impact of inflation on both macroeconomic indicators and financial indicators of enterprises. The

following problems arise in connection with the use of this method:

1. index calculation method;
2. price statistics methodology for creating and correcting indices;
3. selection of basic indicators for the period covered by the analysis;
4. recalculation of selected indicators from real to constant prices using the relevant price index.

The presence of banknotes and coins in circulation is one of the economic categories that cause inflation. The term "inflation" is derived from the Latin word "inflation" which means "inflated", "exaggerated", "increased". The economic essence of inflation means a decrease in the purchasing power of cash in circulation, an increase in the price of goods and services. From the middle of the 19th century, until it was used by economists as an economic term, it was used in medicine to describe a malignant tumor. History has shown that this word is indeed dangerous in every way. Because inflation is not only an increase in the price of goods and services in some individual markets, it is a dangerous phenomenon for the economy as a whole. The economic meaning of the word "inflation" means issuing a lot of money in relation to the goods in circulation and their prices. If we pay attention to history, the increase in other expenses due to war and other disasters is inextricably linked with inflation.

For example, strong inflation was manifested in England at the beginning of the 19th century during the war with Napoleon, in France - during the French Revolution, and in Russia in the middle of the 19th century. Very high inflation in Germany occurred in 1923, when the money in circulation reached 496 quintillion marks and the currency depreciated a trillion times. These historical examples show that inflation is not a current process, but a historical process. Inflation and its development may have specific characteristics in a particular country. The inflation of the current period has different characteristics from the inflation of the past period.

Internal factors of inflation are divided into types related to monetary policy and economic activity. Factors related to economic activity are a violation of balance in the economy and the economy, allowing monopolies in production, cyclical development of the economy, imbalance in investment, monopolies of the state in organizing prices, wrong credit policy. and others, money-related factors include crises in the field of public finances, the state's budget deficit, the growth of public debts, money emission, violations of the law of money circulation, allowing automaticity in lending, etc. The external factors of inflation include crises in the world economy, currency policy of the state (in terms of raw materials, fuel, currency), foreign economic activities of the state with other countries, illegal operations with gold and currency reserves, etc. can be In short, a general or continuous increase in the price of goods and services due to imbalances in the development of production and, as a result, the devaluation of the monetary unit due to the violation of the law of money circulation is called inflation.

Today, inflation targeting is one of the most popular methods of conducting monetary policy, and this method is used in more than 40 countries of the world. The word "Target" is derived from the English language and means "goal". The inflation target is set in the inflation targeting mode. In order to achieve the inflation target, monetary policy mechanisms are gradually transferred to this regime and used as an effective instrument to reduce inflation. In turn, the application of this regime can create additional conditions for strong and sustainable economic growth in the medium term by ensuring price stability. At the same time, the Central Bank determines the most appropriate inflation target and achieves it by using monetary policy instruments, regular analysis of economic development and wide coverage of monetary policy plans.

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